

Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria

Musa Usman^{1,*}, Onipe Adabenege Yahaya²

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the impact of board committees' independence (audit committee independence, nomination committee independence, remuneration committee' independence, and risk committee independence) on intellectual capital efficiency (Value Added Intellectual Capital) of 112 listed firms in Nigeria for the years 2013-2022. The paper applies descriptive, correlation and multiple linear regression analysis on the model. The findings show that audit committee independence has a positive and significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency. Also, the findings show that nomination committee independence has a positive and significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency. Similarly, the findings show that remuneration committee independence has a positive and significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency. Finally, the findings show that risk committee independence has a positive and significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency. Also, in terms of the control variables, leverage, listing age and firm size show positive and significant effects on ICE. This study, therefore, concludes that both audit, nomination, remuneration, risk committee independence, financial leverage, listing age and firm size are determinants of intellectual capital efficiency in Nigeria. These results have important implications for regulators, shareholders, and lenders in that they confirm that the effectiveness of board committees in intellectual capital efficiency is a function of independence. This study, therefore, recommends that regulators, shareholders and lenders pay extra attention to the level of intellectual capital of firms, as this can have long-term growth potentials and implications.

Keywords: Audit Committee Independence, Firm age, Firm size, Intellectual Capital Efficiency, Leverage, Nigeria, Nomination Committee Independence, Remuneration Committee Independence, Risk Committee Independence

JEL Classification: M14, G21, G34, B26.

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1.0 Introduction

A huge body of research speak about the impact of board committees' independence (BCI) on intellectual capital efficiency (ICE). However, prior literature provides only limited evidence of the impact of BCI on ICE. This has developed into corporate concerns regarding the quality and quantity of ICE. With this instability, the demand for better intellectual capital (IC) cannot be over-emphasised. Several more research works are needed on how to improve firms IC. Furthermore, according to the World Bank (2022), Nigeria is ranked number 31 out of 209 countries in terms of gross domestic product (GDP) with a GDP of US\$477,386 million. This position may look fair in terms of arithmetic numbers, however, in terms of GDP, USA leads with US\$27,462,700 million, China (US\$17,963,171 million), Japan (US\$4,231,141 million), Germany (US\$4,072,192 million), India (US\$3,385,090 million), UK (US\$3,070, 668 million), France (US\$2,782,905 million), Russia (US\$4,231,141 million), etc.

*Corresponding author.

¹ Senior Lecturer, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Federal University, Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria. E-mail: musausman@gmail.com

² Associate Professor, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Kaduna State, Nigeria. E-mail: yoadabenege@nda.edu.ng

It is important, at this junction to link the intellectual capital of a country with its GDP. Therefore, that Nigeria is ranked number 31 is not surprising; it simply means that Nigeria is yet to maximize its latent potentials hidden in its IC. IC is often divided into structural capital, human capital, capital employed, and relational capital. However, for the purpose of this paper, IC is seen from perspective of three sources of IC (structural capital, human capital, and capital employed). The sum of these three sources of IC are what this paper refers to as Value Added Intellectual Capital (VAIC), which is the proxy for ICE. Value-added intellectual capital is the measurement of intellectual capital efficiency of a company. It shows the level of value creation efficiency of tangible assets and intangible assets owned by the company.

One of the solutions to instability in intellectual capital being paraded around the world is board committee independence. As part of corporate governance mechanisms, a firm may have several board committees. However, for the purpose of this paper, board committees are divided into four: audit committee, nomination committee, remuneration committee and risk committee. It is important to note that a firm may also constitute sustainability committee. The independence of these committees are the proxies of board committees. Empirical literature place premium on the role of board committees' independence. Independence of a board committee is highly placed among good corporate governance mechanisms. Company boards should have an independent majority. An independent majority on the board is more likely to consider the best interests of shareowners first, allowing agency theory. It also is likely to foster independent decision-making and to mitigate conflicts of interest that may arise.

The role of board committees' independence in improving a firm's ICE is important. Several scholars and researchers have shown interest (Ahmad et al., 2019; Ali & Oudat, 2021; Al-Musalli & Ismail, 2012; Hidalgo et al., 2011; Kweh et al., 2022; Li et al., 2012; Nicholson & Kiel, 2004; Swartz & Firer, 2005; Vitolia et al., 2020; White et al., 2007) among others. However, notwithstanding, most of these works are done in developed countries. Little scholarly works have been done in developing or emerging countries, of which, Nigeria is one. Furthermore, in terms of comparative perspective, less research has examined the effects of board committee independence elements on ICE in Nigeria. Further, no study in literature documents a cross-country examination of BCI and ICE in this region. There is need to carry out additional studies in emerging nations. This is one of the motivations of this paper.

Furthermore, the country is emerging, it requires additional and special attention, in order to actualize its full potential. Therefore, scholars and researchers are expected to carry out additional studies, especially empirical studies in order to provide the foundation, which can be used to compare and contrast future researches. In addition, the paper is of benefit to regulators, shareholders, lenders, students, publics, etc. The paper will also benefit performance, policy and practice. However, the paper is limited by the period covered (2013-2022), variables (audit committee independence, nomination committee independence, remuneration committee independence, and risk committee independence, and intellectual capital efficiency (VAIC: structural capital, human capital and capital employed). The remaining part of this paper comprises of literature review, methodology, results and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations. The literature review consists of conceptual literature, theoretical review and empirical review. Methodology consists of research design, population, sample, model, sources and methods of data collection, methods of analyses, and post estimation tests. Results and discussion cover both descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis. The paper ends with conclusions and recommendations.

2.0 Literature review

The impact of board committees' independence on intellectual capital efficiency has been a topic that has evolved. From the concept of BCI to the concept of ICE, this change in the perception of the role of BCI in ICE has taken its time. BCI refers to the independence of four board committees (audit committee, nomination committee, remuneration committee, and risk committee). Similarly, ICE consists of structural capital efficiency, human capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency. However, the three sources of IC are summed up into IC as value added intellectual capital (VAIC).

This paper relies on the Agency theory. It is a principle that is used to explain and resolve issues in the relationship between business principals and their agents. Most commonly, that relationship is the one between shareholders, as principals, and company executives (in the case of this paper as board committees), as agents. It is the study of challenges and solutions that are connected to the delegation of tasks from the principals to the agents in the context of the conflicting interests between the parties. Agency theory is one of the most widely used theories in empirical accounting and finance papers. Agency theory is used in several research works (for example, Abdulwahab et al., 2023; Appuhami & Bhuyan, 2015; Apochi et al., 2022; Awen et al., 2022a; Awen et al., 2022b; Awen et al., 2023; Bebchuk & Fried, 2003; Berger & Di Patti, 2006; Donaldson & Davis, 1991; Eisenhardt, 1989; Hill & Jones, 1992; Itopa et al., 2022; Lafontaine, 1992; Maury, 2006; Muhanguzi, 2019; Shah, 2014; Shapiro, 2005; Usman & Yahaya, 2023; Wooldridge & Jennings, 1994; Yahaya, 2022a; Yahaya, 2022b; Yahaya & Apochi, 2021; Yahaya & Mohammed, 2022).

In terms of empirical studies, Nicholson and Kiel (2004) provide a model of board effectiveness that is linked with intellectual capital. They further contend that firms that wish to improve their board's effectiveness can do so through intellectual capital. They conclude by linking the model to a practitioner-focused framework that identifies four key

board committees (audit, nomination, remuneration and risk committee), on which a board must concentrate to develop its intellectual capital. Also, Cerbioni and Parbonetti (2008) examine the relationship between governance variables and intellectual capital in a sample of European biotechnology firms. They extend previous research by simultaneously considering governance mechanisms such as the proportion of independent directors, board dimension, CEO duality and board structure in relationship to intellectual capital. Their results show that the proportion of independent directors is positively related to intellectual capital. Whiting and Woodcock (2011) examine the presence of intellectual capital in Australian company reports and the influence of company characteristics (listing age and leverage) on IC. Results show that a company's leverage level and listing age did not influence the occurrence of IC.

Also, Li et al. (2012) use data from 100 UK listed firms to investigate the relationship between audit committee characteristics and intellectual capital (IC). They find no significant relationship between IC and audit committee independence. Ousama et al. (2012) examine the determinants (i.e. firm size, profitability, leverage, type of audit firm and industry type) of intellectual capital (IC) in the annual reports of Malaysian listed companies. The data were collected from the 2006 annual reports of the selected listed companies; and analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-test, correlation and regression analyses. The paper finds that firm size is determinants of IC, while leverage did not statistically influence IC. Furthermore, Al-Musalli and Ismail (2012) examine the relationship between board of directors' characteristics (number of independent directors) and intellectual capital efficiency in a sample of 147 banks in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries for the period 2008-2010. The results show that IC of GCC listed banks is low. In contrast to our expectation, the number of independent directors has a significant negative relationship with IC performance of GCC listed banks.

Said et al. (2013) examine the relationships between board characteristics (board size and board independence), firm characteristics (business type) and human capital characteristics (age, knowledge background and proportion of female directors) in Malaysian public listed companies' annual reports for the year ended 2009. The results of the study reveal that there is a significant relationship between the existence of an independent non-executive chairman and the extent of intellectual capital. Makki and Lodhi (2014) develop a structural model linking board committees and intellectual capital efficiency. The study concludes that board committees enhance it significantly through exploiting intellectual capital resources. Mahmudi and Nurhayati (2014) investigate the influence of board governance characteristics (proportion of board independence and proportion of audit committee independence) to Intellectual Capital of 31 banking companies listed on the Stock Exchange from the year 2008-2012. The result show that there is a significant effect between Intellectual Capital and proportion of board independence, & size of audit committee. We find no influence between Intellectual Capital and proportion of audit committee independence.

Ahmed-Haji (2015) examines the role of audit committee attributes in intellectual capital efficiency. The findings show a strong positive role of the audit committee independence in the overall amount of IC. In contrast, Appuhami and Bhuyan (2015) examine the influence of corporate governance on intellectual capital (IC) in top service firms in Australia. However, there is no evidence that audit committee independence has an effect on IC. Additionally, part of the findings of the regression analysis indicate that remuneration committee independence is significantly associated with IC.

Whiting and Birch (2016) examine whether facets of corporate governance (board size, proportion of independent directors on the board, board committees, and Big 4 auditor) promote the intellectual capital in annual reports in Australia and New Zealand and whether this is country dependent. The presence of nomination committees and a majority of independent directors on the board were found to be significant positive predictors of intellectual capital disclosure in both countries. Buaily (2018) examine the effect of audit committee characteristics on intellectual capital efficiency. The study examined 59 banks for five years (2011-2015), obtaining 295 observations. The findings deduced from the empirical results demonstrate that there is a significant positive impact of audit committee independence on intellectual capital.

Also, Kamath (2019) examines the corporate governance characteristics and its influence on the intellectual capital for a sample of 95 firms listed on National Stock Exchange in India for a 7-year period, i.e. FY2010–2011 to FY2016–2017, using panel regression. The research findings provide clear evidence that independence of directors are seen to have the most significant impacts. Tulung et al. (2019) examine the influence of corporate governance on the intellectual capital of 62 private banks in Indonesia. The variables to be examined in the research include the Composition of Independent Commissioners as well as the Competence of Audit Committee and Risk Oversight Committee. The result of a partial test shows that the Composition of Independent Commissioners has a positive and significant influence on the intellectual capital; the Competence of Audit Committee has a positive and significant influence on the intellectual capital; and the Competence of Risk Oversight Committee does not influence the intellectual capital. Meanwhile, the result of a simultaneous test shows that the Composition of Independent Commissioners, the Competence of Audit Committee, and the Competence of Risk Oversight Committee significantly influence the intellectual capital. Tran et al. (2020) examine the relationship between corporate governance and intellectual capital in the context of Vietnam. Empirical findings from this paper indicate that board remuneration committee has no effect on the efficient use of intellectual capital.

Based on the literature review, this study develops four hypotheses, which are tested. These hypotheses test the impact of board committees on intellectual capital efficiency of listed firms in Nigeria:

H₁: Audit committee independence has no significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency.

H₂: Nomination committee independence has no significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency.

H₃: Remuneration committee independence has no significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency.

H₄: Risk committee independence has no significant effect on intellectual capital efficiency.

On the control variables, Ferreira et al. (2012) analyze annual reports as media of intellectual capital by Portuguese listed companies. Results show that firm size is significant in explaining IC, whereas leverage is not.

The remaining parts of this paper is divided into four: literature review, methodology, results and discussion, and conclusions and recommendations. The part on literature consists of conceptual literature review, theoretical literature review and empirical literature review. The part on methodology consists of research design, population and sample of this paper, model specification, variables definitions and measurements, sources and methods of data collection and analysis techniques and diagnostic tests. The part of section four is results and discussions and finally, section five is on conclusions and recommendations.

3.0 Methodology

The research design is correlational. The NGX 156 listed firms constitute the population of the study. Out of these, 112 companies were selected as sample for our analysis. 44 companies were excluded due to regulatory non-compliance. The selected companies account for more than 71.8 percent of the population. For this research, the sample period selected was from 2013 to 2022. This period has been selected to understand the latest trends and impact of the selected independent variables on the dependent variable. The data for our analysis is sourced from the NGX. This paper uses content analysis technique to calculate the VAIC scores of the firms. This score is divided into sub-categories, which are then added to accumulate the total score. Data has been analyzed using the statistical software STATA 16. Multiple statistical tools, which include Pearson Correlation and Linear Regression, have been used. These methods of analysis have been used to get deep insights into the data and draw relationships. We examine the effect of board committees on intellectual capital efficiency using the following model, derived from the existing literature. Consistent with the previous literature, we use Value Added Intellectual Capital (human capital, structural capital and capital employed) as a measure of intellectual capital efficiency:

$$ICE_{i,t} = \alpha + ACI_{i,t}\beta_1 + NCI_{i,t}\beta_2 + RECI_{i,t}\beta_3 + RICI_{i,t}\beta_4 + LEV_{i,t}\beta_5 + AGE_{i,t}\beta_6 + SIZ_{i,t}\beta_7 + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

ICE = Intellectual capital efficiency, measured by VAIC, which is made up of structural capital, human capital and capital employed.

α = Constant

ACI = Audit committee independence, measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the audit committee divided by audit committee members size (%).

i = Firm script (i = 112 companies)

t = Time script (t = 10 years)

β_{1-7} = Beta coefficients

NCI = Nomination committee independence, measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the nomination committee divided by nomination committee members size (%).

RECI = Remuneration committee independence, measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the remuneration committee divided by remuneration committee members size (%).

RICI = Risk committee independence, measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the risk committee divided by risk committee members size (%).

LEV = Leverage, measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.

AGE = Listing age, measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.

SIZ = Firm size, measured as natural log of total asset.

ε = Idiosyncratic error term.

In order to analyze the role of board committees' independence in ICE, we use audit committee independence, nomination committee independence, remuneration committee independence, and risk committee independence. As discussed earlier, independence of board committees can potentially have both positive and negative effects on ICE. However, as per our stated hypotheses, we predict a positive relationship between board committees' independence and ICE. Although, we are investigating how board committees' independence can influence the extent of ICE, there are other firm level factors that can influence ICE and which require to be controlled for in the estimations. On the basis of earlier studies, we consider financial leverage (*LEV*), firm's size (*SIZ*), and firm listing age (*AGE*) in a firm as the control variables. The remaining parts of this paper is divided into two sections: results and discussion, and conclusions and recommendations. The part of section four is results and discussions and finally, section five is on conclusions and recommendations.

4. Empirical Results

As mentioned in section three (methodology), our sample consists of the 112 listed firms that trade in the NGX, accounting for about 71.8 percent of the population. Summary measures of variables of interest are presented in Table 1. The core research question in this paper is to assess whether board committees' independence lead to higher ICE? Furthermore, we talk about the effects of the control variables on ICE in this section.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
VAIC	1120	3.333	1.633	1.81	10.52
ACI	1120	50.351	4.866	42.857	100
NCI	1120	15.136	34.465	0	100
RECI	1120	28.266	42.193	0	100
RICI	1120	41	37.225	0	100
LEV	1120	86.816	18.823	8.63	254.75
AGE	1120	22.545	15.488	2	50
SIZ	1120	8.963	.461	8.03	10.77

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Table 1 shows that the number of firm-year observations is 1,120, which is 112 firms multiplied by 10 years (2013-2022). The average of VAIC is 3.333 point, with a standard deviation of 1.633, minimum and maximum mean of 1.81 and 10.52, respectively, which suggests that VAIC is not highly volatile. Furthermore, the average of ACI is 50.351 percent, with a standard deviation of 4.866 percent, minimum and maximum mean of 42.857 and 100 percent, respectively, which also suggests that there is no variability in ACI. Similarly, the average of NCI is 15.136 percent, with a standard deviation of 34.465 percent, minimum and maximum mean of 0 and 100 percent, respectively. The standard deviation is higher than the mean, suggesting that NCI is highly volatile. Furthermore, the average of RECI is 28.266 percent, with a standard deviation of 42.193 percent, minimum and maximum mean of 0 and 100 percent, respectively, which suggests that RECI is highly volatile. In addition, the average of RICI is 41 percent, with a standard deviation of 37.225 percent, minimum and maximum mean of 0 and 100 percent, respectively. By a comparison of the mean and standard deviation, one can observe that the standard deviation is not far from the mean, suggesting that RICI is not stable.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the three control variables. The mean of LEV is 86.816 percent, with a standard deviation of 18.823 percent, minimum and maximum mean of 8.63 and 254.75 percent, respectively, which shows that financial leverage (gearing) is high. In the same vein, the average of listing AGE is about 23 years, with a standard deviation of about 16 years, minimum and maximum mean of 2 and 50 years, respectively. Finally, in terms of firm size, the average of SIZ is 8.963 point, with a standard deviation of .461, minimum and maximum mean of 8.03 and 10.77 point, respectively. Table 2 presents the results of normality of residuals test,

Table 2
Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
r	1120	0.89826	71.148	10.610	0.00000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Table 2 shows that the residuals is not normally distributed, since the p-value is less than .05. The next logical step is to try to transform the data, the results of transformation test is in Table 3.

Table 3
Model transformation

Transformation	formula	chi2 (2)	P (chi2)
cubic	r^3	.	.
square	r^2	.	.
identity	r	.	0.000
square root	\sqrt{r}	.	.
log	$\log(r)$.	.
1/(square root)	$1/\sqrt{r}$.	.
inverse	$1/r$.	.
1/square	$1/(r^2)$.	.
1/cubic	$1/(r^3)$.	.

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The results in Table 3 show that the model is not transformable, suggesting that the only way to make its residuals normal is to robust the model. Table 4 shows the results of correlation matrix for the purpose of testing multicollinearity among the board committees' independence.

Table 4
Correlation matrix

	VAIC	ACI	NCI	RECI	RICI	LEV	AGE
VAIC	1.0000						
ACI	0.0220 0.4624	1.0000					
NCI	-0.0158 0.5967	0.0318 0.2884	1.0000				
RECI	-0.0409 0.1719	-0.0446 0.1359	0.2840* 0.0000	1.0000			
RICI	0.0052 0.8618	0.0169 0.5718	-0.0124 0.6785	-0.0493 0.0988	1.0000		
LEV	-0.0539 0.0713	-0.0041 0.8914	-0.0351 0.2407	0.0316 0.2904	0.0312 0.2969	1.0000	
AGE	-0.0723* 0.0155	-0.0149 0.6191	-0.0412 0.1681	0.0317 0.2898	0.0608* 0.0421	0.1070* 0.0003	1.0000
SIZ	0.3133* 0.0000	-0.0214 0.4735	0.0512 0.0868	-0.0032 0.9144	-0.0103 0.7302	-0.2144* 0.0000	0.2893* 0.0000
		SIZ					
SIZ	1.0000						

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Table 4 shows that none of the coefficients is up to 0.80, suggesting that there is multicollinearity among the board committees' independence. However, in order to confirm these results, Table 5 shows that variance inflation factors of the independent variables.

Table 5

Variance inflation factors

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
SIZ	1.18	0.850925
AGE	1.14	0.878131
NCI	1.10	0.909412
RECI	1.10	0.910251
LEV	1.09	0.921367
RICI	1.01	0.992142
ACI	1.01	0.995020
Mean VIF	1.09	

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 5, the VIFs are less than 10, confirming that there is no multicollinearity among the board committees' independence and control variables. Table 6 shows the results of heteroskedasticity of residuals test.

Table 6

Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	117.11	35	0.0000
Skewness	44.39	7	0.0000
Kurtosis	13.00	1	0.0003
Total	174.50	43	0.0000

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From the results in Table 6, the p-value of heteroskedasticity is significant, meaning it is less than .05, this suggests that the model has het problem. The answer to it is to robust the final model of the paper. Table 7 reports the results of the final regression, having taken into accounts the results of the diagnostic tests.

Table 7

Linear regression

VAIC	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf Interval]	Sig
ACI	.009	.012	0.77	.0441	-.014 .033	**
NCI	.002	.001	1.17	.0244	-.005 .001	**
RECI	.001	.001	0.74	.0458	-.003 .001	**
RICI	.001	.001	0.65	.014	-.002 .003	**
LEV	.004	.004	1.12	.0263	-.003 .011	**
AGE	.02	.002	8.00	.000	-.025 -.015	***
SIZ	1.348	.109	12.34	.000	1.134 1.563	***
Constant	-9.098	1.27	-7.17	.0	-11.589 -6.607	***
Mean dependent var		3.333	SD dependent var		1.633	
R-squared		0.733	Number of obs		1120	
F-test		131.197	Prob > F		0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		4132.508	Bayesian crit. (BIC)		4172.677	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From Table 7, the Prob > F is significant, suggesting that the model is fit and can be used for the analysis. Furthermore, as indicated by Table 7, the R^2 is .733, meaning that about 73 percent of the variation in ICE is explained by the model. In addition, Table 7 shows that ACI has both positive and significant effects on ICE, which are consistent with our *a priori* expectation. Also, Table 7 shows that NCI has both positive and significant effects on ICE, which are consistent with our *a priori* expectation. Furthermore, Table 7 shows that RECI has both positive and significant effects on ICE, which are consistent with our *a priori* expectation. Similarly, Table 7 shows that RICI has both positive and significant effects on ICE, which are consistent with our *a priori* expectation. These results are consistent with the results of some scholars (Al-Musalli & Ismail, 2012; Bually, 2018; Cerbioni & Parabonelli, 2008; Kamath, 2019; Mahmudi & Nurhayati, 2014; Makki & Lodhi, 2014; Nicholson & Kiel, 2004; Ousama et al., 2012; Said et al., 2013; Tran et al., 2020; Tulung et al., 2019; Whiting & Birch, 2016; Whiting & Woodcock, 2011). In terms of control variables, Table 7 shows that LEV, AGE, and SIZ have both positive and significant effects on ICE, which are consistent with our *a priori* expectation. These results are consistent with the results of some scholars (Ferreira et al., 2012; Li et al., 2012; Ousama et al., 2012). These results mean that firms with large size, show significantly greater ICE. All of these results are confirming the previous literature. However, although leverage increases ICE as expected on the basis of earlier studies, the result calls for further investigation because it is high.

5.0 Conclusions and recommendations

The general purpose of this study is to provide econometric analysis of the association between four board committees' independence and intellectual capital efficiency. These four board committees' independence are (1) audit committee independence, (2) nomination committee independence, (3) remuneration committee independence, and (4) risk committee independence. Consistent with the bulk of prior research, the present study defines intellectual capital efficiency the concept of Value Added Intellectual Capital. In a nut shell, the paper tries to find out the relationship between board committees' independence and the intellectual capital efficiency of listed

firms in Nigeria. Board committees' independence is measured by considering four board committees (audit committee independence, nomination committee independence, remuneration committee independence, and risk committee independence). ICE is measured by VAIC, which is made up of structural capital, human capital and capital employed by the firms. Eleven sectors were chosen such as agriculture, conglomerate, financial services, oil and gas, services, consumer goods, industrial goods, construction/real estate, health care, ICT, and natural resources. From the analysis of the collected data, the findings show that audit committee independence, nomination committee independence, remuneration committee independence, and risk committee independence are determinants of ICE. Hence, it can be concluded that as the listed firms grow in size, they ought to create more board committees as earlier mentioned.

The results from this study have established new findings for the listed firms in Nigeria and with this, listed firms in Nigeria should focus on how to manage their resources to reach optimum level of board committees. The findings from this study can be used as clear evidence that ICE level is affected by audit committee independence, nomination committee independence, remuneration committee independence, risk committee independence, firm size, leverage, and age, which means that as the firms grow in size and the number of directors increases, they tend to create more board committees, which should be independent, that is, largely made up of independent directors.

This paper contributes to the existing literature by analyzing all the sectors that play major roles in the economy of Nigeria. A future direction of study to enhance the existing literature can be to incorporate more variables, such as sustainability committee independence. The number of observations can be increased, by considering a larger study period.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express gratitude to the various parties that have assisted in this paper. In particular, the authors wish to thank Professor Muhammad Tanko, Professor Aliyu Suleiman Kantudu, Professor Muhammad Liman Muhammad, Professor Isa Dandago, and Professor Muhammad Barde for their advice and suggestions. Also, the authors wish to express their gratitude to the participants in the International Accounting Conference for their remarks.

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